

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: WATIRO****FIRST NAME: AKLILU HABTE****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 8%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the principal role of a style guide in written communication, particularly in essays, and how do academic essays specifically differ from other types of essays in terms of their style guides?¹

- The primary role of style in essay writing is to make writing more creative and spontaneous, while academic essays differ in that they are longer than others.
- The primary purpose of style in essay writing is to maintain a consistent approach to various writing elements. Academic essays, however, are uniquely characterized by their reliance on evidence to support answers to specific research questions or hypotheses.**

1. Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fifth Edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 41.

- The primary role of style in essay writing is to replace the need for proofreading, while academic essays differ from others in that they are written in a formal tone.
2. What are a research argument's essential components or core elements, and how are these elements typically defined and structured within academic research?²
- Topic, question, and significance are core components of a research argument, where the topic serves as the main idea of our research. The question, in contrast, is described as a claim that must be explored to delve into the topic thoroughly. Significance, on the other hand, provides the reasoning or justification for seeking an answer to the research question
 - Introduction, body, and conclusion are the basic structure of academic research, where the introduction details the problem statement and provides a road map for the research argument. The body of the study serves as the building block for our argument. On the other hand, the conclusion summarizes the main points and provides a final broad statement.
 - The essential parts of a research argument are the claim, reasons, and evidence. A claim is a proposed, debatable answer, potentially originating from imaginative thought. Reasons are the justifications for this claim, and evidence is the data that grounds these justifications.**
 - Hypothesis, data, and summary are core components of research. A hypothesis can be understood as a tentative answer formulated in response to your research

2. Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 58.

- question. Data refers to the recorded factual material utilized to validate and support findings within a study. A summary is a concise overview designed to present the main points of a research or article.
3. According to the Turabian guide, what is the general procedure for citing a source in notes after it has been cited fully for the first time?³
- The full citation must be repeated every time.
 - Only the page number is needed.
 - The term “op. cit.” is always used.
 - A shortened form, like the author’s last name and a shortened title.**
4. According to Turabian citation of specific types of sources, how should titles of books and journals generally be formatted in citations?⁴
- In quotation marks.
 - In bold text.
 - In italics.**
 - In all capital letters.
5. What instruction applies to quoting prose extending to five or more lines in Turabian’s quotation style?⁵

3. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers*, 163.

4. Ibid., 154.

5. Ibid., 372.

- Run it into the text and enclose it in double quotation marks.
 - Run it into the text and enclose it in single quotation marks.
 - Set it off as an indented block quotation, without quotation marks.**
 - Summarize the quotation instead of quoting it directly.
6. According to the dissertation research guide, what key elements contribute to a successful dissertation?⁶
- Ensure good communication with the major professor, supervisory committee, and significant others.**
 - Working in complete isolation to avoid external bias.
 - Strict adherence to the initial research plan without any deviation.
 - Focusing solely on quantitative methods for more objective results.
7. Based on the dissertation research guide, what details or content are the ideal requirements for the dissertation title?⁷
- Solely toward the principal variable being examined.
 - A catchy phrase to attract readers.
 - The variables, participants, and setting for the research (or treatment, variables, participants, and setting).**
 - The name of the primary author and their university.

6. James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 13.

7. *Ibid.*, 24.

8. Among the given statements and options, which statement accurately describes measurement bias as it occurs in instruments, tests, or questionnaires, and which option is NOT a potential source of bias in dissertation research?⁸

- Measurement bias does not affect the capacity of instruments to measure constructs for intended norm groups, while selection preference is considered a source of bias.
- Construct-irrelevant aspects of test scores can enhance the accuracy of test scores for specific groups, even though experience could be considered a source of bias.
- Documenting evidence of bias in creating test items is unnecessary to ensure fairness across different demographic groups, even though the type of population could be considered a source of bias in the dissertation.
- Expert practitioner panels can evaluate if disparities among participant groups are due to actual differences or biased elements within the study. On the other hand, random sampling is a technique used to reduce the impact of potential bias.**

9. What specific spacing rule does the English style guide recommend for punctuation marks directly after a word, letter, or number?⁹

- Always leave a space before punctuation marks.
- They are always close to the preceding word, letter, or number (except for dashes and ellipsis points).**

8. Sampson, *Dissertation Research Guide*, 46.

9. European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth Edition (Brussels: European Union Publications Office, 2021), 7.

- It depends on the specific punctuation mark.
- A double space should follow stops.

10. What does the term ‘acquis’ refer to in the context of the EU?¹⁰

- Only the primary legislation (Treaties).
- Only the secondary legislation adopted under the Treaties.
- The body of EU law broadly includes Treaties, legislation, case-law, declarations, and international agreements.**
- The financial budget of the European Union.

10. European Commission, *English Style Guide*, 71–72.

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